

The Digital Layer in the Human Resources Management: An Overview of the Human Resources Management System

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Abstract: This article would provide an overview of human resource management related computer system commonly referred as Human Resources Management System (HRMS). HRMS is the primary focus of this article as HRMS captures and distributes a wide variety of financial and HR data. System data and functionality support HR practices, employee benefits, labor management, financial management, and strategic planning across the organization. The HRMS coordinates HR, payroll, and financial data for the employees, and collects and maintains recruitment information, performance, and employee's personnel files. And many other things. The data can be accessed anytime for appraisal or evaluation.

Key word: Human Resources Management System (HRMS); HR Management & Computer; IT Enabled HR Management; HR Management Tools.

INTRODUCTION

The ultimate goal of human resources is to improve the efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity of the workforce. However, none of the basic administrative duties can be neglected without serious consequences. To achieve and enhance workforce excellence, organizations need to shift the focus of HR from administrative tasks to strategic program delivery. HR leaders must work with senior management to develop a comprehensive HCM strategy, and then roll out new processes supported by leading technologies. With a successful execution of the HCM strategy, they can then gain support for further HCM strategy initiatives. People are the most important asset in a business. Businesses are paying more attention to the contributions made by their workers and it's paying off on the bottom line. People-related costs now constitute the majority of total corporate expenditures, and leading firms have embraced the need to better manage their human capital and build a more effective workforce. (Oracle, 2009).

Establishing and monitoring internal controls over human resource (HR) information are important management functions. Internal control is fundamental to addressing risks to the completeness and accuracy of information and thus providing assurance over the reliability of HR information, its compliance with applicable laws and regulations and the effectiveness and efficiency of operations. Increasingly, entities are utilizing Human Resource Management Information Systems (HRMIS) to assist in managing their workforce and in meeting their employer obligations. The effective discharge of these responsibilities is necessary to support the development and implementation of government programs and activities. However, the integration of technology to support managing a modern workforce can introduce a range of information management risks. Therefore, it would need to emphasize the important role of both system and manual controls in maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of HR information. (McPhee, 2011). HR technology is increasingly being used by small, medium, and large employers to meet the needs of its stakeholders. Technology sets high-performing organizations apart from others is how they use technology to deliver HR services.

HR technology can be defined as any technology that is used to attract, hire, retain, and maintain human resources, support HR administration, and optimize HRM. This technology can be used in different types of human resource information systems (HRIS) and by various stakeholders, such as managers, employees, and HR professionals. This technology can be accessed in different ways. There is no doubt that technology has made it easier and faster to gather, collate, and deliver information and communicate with employees. More importantly, it has the potential to reduce the administrative burden on the HR department so it is better able to focus on more meaningful HR activities, such as providing managers with the expertise they need to make more effective HR related decisions. Research has indicated that companies who effectively use technology to manage their HR functions will have a significant advantage over those that do not. (Bulmash, 2009).

Human resources, information systems (HRIS) can play an important part in a company's HR function. After all, we live, work and play in the information age. Implementing an effective HRIS can be sure-fire for HR to stay on the cutting edge in its bid to deliver more effective and streamlined service. The main conclusion of this paper is the realization that the use of computerized HRIS is more effective than manual because its help to maintain data with more accuracy in less time. And that it's also true that HRIS functions improve HRM in terms of administrative purposes and analytical purposes. HRIS work as a key component of the organization and a good HRIS will provide important information about human resources needs and capabilities; this information will assist the management team in establishing the organizational mission and setting goals and objectives in motion. HRIS is not limited to the computer hardware and software applications that comprise the technical part of the system: it also includes the people, policies, procedures and data required to manage the HR function. (Gupta, 2013).

Development of the unified HRMIS standards and their introduction into the public sector is one of the ways for dealing with many problems. Such standard would significantly facilitate development and introduction of higher quality and effective automated solutions. At the same time, the unified standard will be the guarantee of compatibility of the software used in various institutions and this would governmental authorities to promptly obtain accurate information about the situation in the system. (Civil Service Bureau, 2011)

Human resource planning implies a broad spectrum of activities touching many parts of an organization. The focus of human resource planning is on decision support and policy making. It is concerned with aggregate flows of people into, within, and out of the organization and with coordination of persons and jobs on an individual level. (RJ, 1979). *Hercus* (1993) summarizes human resource planning by stating that it is a management process involving the following elements: - forecasting human resource requirements for an organization to execute its business plan; - forecasting human resources available for meeting these needs and doing a scan of the internal and external environments of the organization; - identifying the gaps between what will be needed and what will be available and developing the necessary action plans to bridge the gaps; - implementing and monitoring these actions plans. (I, 1993)

Human Resource Management Systems has achieved its purpose. It has taken a huge task for this project to be completed. It has given a huge lift to the company's operations. Whatever that has done manually has been completely shifted to the computerized process and this has enabled the company to carry out its operation more quickly. This has also given a wider spectrum of communication to the users. Since whatever that has so far been done has been manually changed to a computerized. It has resulted in more efficient processing of data. The new system has resulted in giving numeric advantages to the company in many ways. Some of them are given below the state of negligible paperwork is almost reduced. Accessing and getting data can be done in a single click. Data manipulation has become simpler and the cost factor has been reduced. It is faster and more efficient processing of data. It is less time consuming. Operations are more transparent. Communications between the users is more efficient. (A.S.Syed Navaz, 2013).

AN OVERVIEW OF AN HRMS

There are many HRMS in the market and used by different organizations. Even there are many compartmentalized systems working differently for different functions. There are even different systems for recruitment, pay, attendance, leave, and some other functions. Even there are all integrated into one HR management as a suite. Even all segmented systems can be integrated online or through a server and a database.

One of the advantages of such software has been that it can produce timely and accurate reports about the specific functions as well as coordinates with the respective personnel, payroll, and financial data. It also provides access to system data and functionality. All managers who have been given the appropriate security can access HRMS either using the internet or intranet. Most of HRMS available in the market does sustain business intelligence and can retain historical records of HRMS data to generate a variety of reports.

Usually any Human Resources Management Systems (HRMS) remained divided into many functional components that may vary according to need, urgency, and utility. In general, an HRMS does have functional components such as Organizational Management, Personnel Administration, Payroll processing, and time management. All those components are firmly integrated with each other. Data entered into any component flows throughout the system to those processes that use the data. The organizational management component creates and maintains agency's organizational structures and their units, positions, and jobs. The personnel administration component creates and maintains information about employees. It may have the processes related to hiring, changes, separations, and absences. The payroll processing component usually calculates earnings and payment-related items for employees and vendors. It also processes benefit and financial transactions, which includes sending and receiving information to and from other state systems. The time management component creates and maintains a work schedule to track employee hours (attendances and absences) used to pay employees.

Every HRMS does have certain security many times specific to a particular organization considering the structure and role, and functions of different managers. Security arrangements can be embedded into the system considering the environments, transactions, and info types that a user can access or update. Roles can be either centralized or decentralized. HRMS roles are key to HRMS security and to agency business processes.

Centralized functional roles enable central support to agencies in emergencies and assure successful payroll operations. They allow to oversee and modify various tables in HRMS. Centralized functional roles also allow the Department of Retirement Systems, Health Care Authority, and Attorney General's Office to perform their authorized HRMS benefits and oversight roles state wide.

Centralized oversight and management roles allow the Office of Financial Management to oversee HRMS data and activities. These roles also allow to perform maintenance and development processes, and transfers approved configuration changes to the production environments. They allow to initiate the payroll process. Centralized security roles allow to create and assign security roles, user IDs and passwords, and perform audits to security role assignments.

Decentralized roles provide access, by functional area (Personnel Administration, Payroll, Garnishment, Benefits, Leave, Time and Attendance, Financial, and Organization Management). Decentralized Security roles allow the assignment of decentralized user roles, user IDs and passwords, and oversight functions.

Each agency has designated HRMS Security Administrators who are responsible for maintaining agency role assignments and password maintenance. When new employees are hired, HRMS generates their personnel numbers (user ID) and distributes their initial passwords. DOP provides support for centralized state wide access, provides support and training for decentralized agency HRMS security administrators, and assists with troubleshooting for HRMS security issues. Role Definition Handbooks provide information about how the different HRMS Roles relate to a user's access to system data and transactions. Required training is provided for users based on their roles.

HRMS Training is provided to selectively employee or managers based on roles. Users need training for each of the roles assigned by their agency. The majority of these employees perform human resources, payroll, and time and attendance functions. In addition to online and classroom training, access to course manuals, job aids, user procedures, and other materials that can be accessed by users to understand and perform their work. The On-Line Quick Reference (OLQR) contains instructional materials organized by functional areas, a glossary, job aids, and step-by-step user procedures that describe how to perform HRMS tasks. Some agencies or departments can maintain applications for various HR, payroll, or time functions that support agency business practices. Interfaces are electronic files or reports that move data between computer applications. There are several critical HRMS interfaces that support important processes (e.g., the Office of Financial Management's financial systems, Department of Retirement Systems, and Health Care Authority). Interfaces are sometimes referred to as GAPS.

There are two types of HRMS interfaces inbound and outbound. An inbound interface is used when HRMS receives data from agencies or other sources. Time & Leave Activity interface can provide input from agencies who have their own shadow systems for recording employee hours worked and leave activities. Whereas, outbound interfaces are used when HRMS sends data to agencies or other destinations. Employee Master Data can provide agencies a report of daily activity of HR data and cost distribution master data.

Incident, Change, and Release Management

An HRMS can be used for managing incidents, change, and release. All incidents affecting the production HRMS environment can be tracked. Incidents may be events that do or have the potential to interrupt or reduce service, or requests for help in processing a transaction or clarifying system functionality. Incidents may be reported by client agencies, staff, or other stakeholders who interact with HRMS. The Service Center is the point of contact for agency HRMS users. An electronic tracking system can be used to manage incidents to completion. Incidents are prioritized for resolution, and may be transitioned to Change/Release Management process if they involve a change to the HRMS production environment.

System changes can affect multiple users, disrupt services, affect stored data, or involve hardware or software. To reduce risk, all change requests (CRs) are reviewed, prioritized, and tracked to completion. All changes required to monitor the processes and workflows, identifies stakeholders, assigns severity levels, coordinates implementation, monitoring and reporting, and manages escalation.

Release Management (RM) is the process of planning, creating, testing, and implementing software releases. Applications like HRMS are frequently updated to meet new legal, technical, and business requirements. These updates, or “new releases,” often require system downtime, and can affect user procedures or business processes. RM “bundles” several approved changes (change requests) in one monthly release, similar to the updates that Microsoft provides for Windows and Office products. This process coordinates the changes to keep it current and running well, and lets users know what changes to expect and when. The RM process also provides for exceptions and emergency updates that must be implemented outside of the RM schedule because mission critical applications will not process unless the change is implemented, or the change has a specific timeframe.

Using and Transacting Through HRMS

Professional users log onto HRMS to perform the everyday business tasks for their agency and employees. It would allow the user to drill down to a desired functional area to create, change, display, or delete information, or run reports. Users can open multiple HRMS sessions in order to work on more than one employee record at the same time. Toolbar buttons throughout the system allow users to move from screen to screen, save, or cancel entries, display data in different ways, and complete transactions.

A transaction is a set of tasks performed in HRMS to complete a business process, such as viewing or changing employee information, and running reports. Each transaction is assigned a transaction code which provides access to the initial screen of the transaction.

There are transactions to create or maintain organizational structures, jobs, positions, and cost information. There are transactions to hire, change, and separate employees.

Personnel Number

All employees have a system-generated Personnel Number in HRMS which protects employee information yet maintains a unique record for the employee. Prior to generating new Personnel Numbers, agencies are instructed to search HRMS and the Data Warehouse to see if the person had previously worked in order to avoid multiple Personnel Numbers for the same employee. Employees who work with multiple agencies concurrently will have one primary Personnel Number and a Reference Number to maintain their employee records.

Reports

HRMS reports are available, according to role, across functional areas and provide data that relates to business tasks, and are filtered so that agencies view only their own data. HRMS data is live and accurate at the

time it was accessed. There are Standard and Customized HRMS reports. Standard reports are included with the SAP software and provide data sets that are commonly used by most employers. Customized reports are created to satisfy unique requirements. Agencies can create report variants so that selected information is saved and can be generated on a regular basis. Reports are accessed by entering the transaction code for the desired report and can be printed or exported to Excel where it can be manipulated in order to view or work with specific data.

In addition to the HRMS reports, *Business Intelligence (BI)* is a resource for historical HRMS data and offers a selection of standard reports. Users can create ad hoc queries for their agency's business process requirements. HRMS provides periodic downloads to keep BI data current.

Known differences among HRMS

In order to successfully migrate from one information system to another, it is critical to perform a thorough comparison of data fields and functions between the two systems to identify the known differences. Modern software (such as HRMS) is written in high level programming languages and is usually designed by the manufacturer to run on a variety of platforms. Older systems may provide vital business needs, but they may not be portable because they are tied to their specific hardware and operating systems. Additionally, some of these vital business needs may not be met by standard commercial, off-the-shelf (COTS) packages, even after customization.

After customization of HRMS, many known differences can be identified, analyzed, and prioritized to determine the best solutions. Many known differences may be addressed by creating user procedures that instruct users in a preferred workaround process.

SOME WELL-KNOWN HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS ENTERPRISE-WIDE SYSTEMS

An enterprise-wide system is also called an enterprise resource planning or ERP system. It has been defined as a system that supports enterprise-wide or cross-functional requirements, rather than a single department or group within the organization. These ERP systems have their origin in software that integrates information from different applications (modules) into one universal database. This means that financial information can be linked to HR information through one database. The most popular high-end enterprise-wide systems are *SAP*, *PeopleSoft*, and *Oracle*.

SAP was founded as *Systemanalyse und Programmentwicklung* in 1972 by five former IBM employees in Mannheim, Germany. This acronym was changed to *Systeme, Anwendungen und Produkte in der Datenverarbeitung*, which means "systems, applications, and products in data processing," and in 2005, the company name was officially changed to *SAP AG*. *SAP* is the world's third-largest software company and its head office is in Walldorf, Germany. In terms of revenue, *SAP* is the largest business application and ERP solutions provider. The company's main product is SAP R/3, the "R" stands for real-time data processing and the number "3" relates to a three-tiered system—database, application server, and client.

SAP products are used by more than 12 million people in more than 120 countries, and its market has typically been Fortune 500 companies. Recently *SAP* has targeted small- to medium-sized organizations with some of its new products. *SAP* is made up of individual, integrated software modules that perform various organizational system tasks such as finance/accounting, controlling, project system, funds management, materials management, and sales distribution. One of its major modules is Human Resource Management Systems (HRMS/HRIS). These systems are very sophisticated and *SAP* offers a full range of functionality, HR products, and Web-based offerings.

PeopleSoft is software that provides HRMS, manufacturing, financial, enterprise performance management, and student administration software solutions to large corporations and governments. The company was founded in 1987 by *David Duffied* and *Ken Morris*. Its software is made up of modules, such as HRMS, which includes payroll, all human resources functions and benefits, financials, manufacturing, student administration, and customer relationship management. *PeopleSoft* is well known for its ability to be easily customized to fit the specific business needs of each client. *PeopleSoft* was acquired by Oracle in 2005. The system enables employees to add dependents to health insurance, change payroll deductions, enroll in benefits programs, calculate pension benefits, and carry out retirement planning.

STANDALONE SOFTWARE

Not all organizations require a sophisticated system and there are many different vendors in the marketplace who offer every size and type of product imaginable. Some considerations for organizations include cost, the number of employees, the degree of efficiency, and the company's existing hardware and software. An effective HRIS requires a balance between what it can do from a technical perspective and how it can meet the needs of that organization. These needs typically increase with the size of the organization.

Smaller firms might use very basic software applications, such as Microsoft Excel and Access. These firms might only require payroll and benefits administration, time and attendance, and employee scheduling functions. Midsize firms typically require compliance tracking and reporting, health claims administration, payroll, compensation, and benefit administration. Managers may require information on performance appraisal, time and attendance, succession planning, skills testing, and employee scheduling, and employees may use the system to aid in career development and self-serve applications. Midsize firms require greater data integration and better backup and recovery capability. In addition, they have many users and require local area network and server-based operations. Typically in these midsize systems, all HRIS functions flow through the single system; therefore, data redundancies can be identified and eliminated.

Some popular HRIS for small to midsize organizations are sold by such vendors as Spectrum Human Resource Management Systems, Genesys Software Systems, Best Software Inc., Ultimate Software (UltiPro workforce management), People Track Inc., and Organization Plus.

Large organizations typically require greater functionality than midsize firms. In addition to those functions mentioned above, large firms will require employee screening, résumé processing and tracking, additional compliance and reporting (such as employment equity), and ESS and MSS for employees and managers. These firms also have a greater need to integrate the HRIS with enterprise wide software applications. Larger organizations might purchase SAP, PeopleSoft, or Oracle ERP systems.

SPECIALTY SOFTWARE

With so many vendors in the marketplace, software can be purchased for virtually any HR-related functions in any industry, including training and development, performance management, succession planning, and the creation of organizational charts. The Entrepreneurs and HR box provide an example of one such company, Cronus Technologies, which is based in Saskatoon, Saskatchewan. Organizations can purchase these applications as stand-alone systems. Specialty software applications are available from Halogen, ExecuTRAK, Org Plus, and Ergowatch.

CONCLUSION

Human Resources Management Systems (HRMS) or Human Resources Information System (HRIS) has become a mandatory for almost all large and middle business. Small business can afford to work with some minor software, including MS Excel also. HRMS is available in different components also for discharging specific human resources functions. Even those components can be integrated together to form a suit. Such systems may be interconnected using the internet or intranet and still can work on a single PC.

VITAE

The Author has worked as Divisional Program Manager under the aegis of the *National Rural Health Mission* with the Jharkhand Government. He has remained an ICSSR doctoral and postdoctoral fellows. Taught students at the UG and PG levels subject, such as HR Management and Organizational Behavior.

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